
Antiproliferative and Structural Activities Relationship Studies of Novel Chalcones and their Derivatives

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Abstract The cytotoxicity and *in vitro* anticancer evaluation of the compounds (**1**, **3a-e**, **4**, **5a-5b** and **6**) have been assessed towards two different human tumor cell lines including human non-small cell lung (A549) and melanoma skin (A375) cancer cell lines in addition to BALB/3T3 (murine fibroblast) normal cell line. The results showed that the *in vitro* antiproliferative activity of the newly synthesized compounds was significant and may be investigated for further *in vivo* and pharmacokinetic studies. Chalcones **3d** was synthesized at the reaction of ketone **1** and 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde in alcoholic KOH respectively. Also, the reaction of Chalcone **3c** was reacted with hydrazine hydrate /or phenyl hydrazine/ or thiourea respectively proceeded the Pyrazole rings **5a,b** & dihydropyrimidine-2(1*H*)-thione **6**.

Keywords lung A549; Skin A375, Chalcones, Pyrazole, thiopyrimidine

Introduction

Although there have been great advances in the detection and treatment of cancer, there is medical challenges still exists, which the incidence of some malignancies is continuing to increase. For many tumor types, established treatments such as cytotoxic chemotherapy and radiotherapy provide only transient therapeutic benefits, yet despite severe side effects. Therefore, the need for better treatments has stimulated research to develop new efficient chemotherapeutic agents for management of cancer [1].

It is known that Chalcones [2, 3] are found in natural plants and Chalcones have interesting pharmacological activities and considered important starting materials for proceed of new heterocyclic compounds with biological activities. The most common and widely used strategy in the synthesis of Chalcones or their analogous. Chalcones are very important starting materials in organic chemistry [4] to afford many heterocyclic rings. This works about the synthesis of Chalcones from ketone with an aldehyde compounds.

In the same direction and in continuing effort to find more potent and selective anticancer compounds, herein, we designed and synthesized a series of compounds (**1**, **3a-e**, **4**, **5a-5b** and **6**). Moreover, there *in vitro* antiproliferative activity towards two different human non-small cell lung(A549) and melanoma skin (A375) cancer cell lines in addition to BALB/3T3 (murine fibroblast) normal cell line was evaluated.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Chemistry

All melting points are uncorrected and were taken on electro-thermal capillary melting point apparatus. The melting points were measured in degrees centigrade and determined using Buchi 510 apparatus. Elemental analyses were carried out in the micro analytical unit in the National Research Centre. IR spectra were recorded on a Mattson-5000 FTIR spectrometer using KBr Wafer technique. ¹H NMR spectra were determined on a Varian-Gemini300 MHz and JeolEx-300 MHz NMR spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard with (chemical shift $\delta = 0$ ppm). Mass Spectra were determined on Finnegan MatSSQ 7000 mode: EI, 70Ev (Thermo Inst. Sys. Inc., USA). The purity of the synthesized compounds was tested by thin layer chromatography (TLC), Merck plates. TLC Silica gel 60 F254 25 Aluminum sheets 20 x 20 cm.

General procedure of Claisen-Schmidt condensation

To a stirred solution of aldehyde compounds **2d** (1 mmol) in EtOH (2.5 mL) was added aqueous 8M KOH (1-6 equivalent). This mixture was stirred for 10 min, followed by addition of the chalcone (1.5 equivalents). The mixture was gradually warmed up to room temperature until Chalcones **3d** was completely consumed according to TLC analysis. At the end of the reaction time, the mixture was quenched by 2 N HCl, diluted with H₂O and extracted with CH₂Cl₂.

1-(6-hydroxy-4,7-dimethoxybenzofuran-5-yl)-3-(5-methylfuran-2-yl)prop-2-en-1-one **3d**:

Brown solid, yield 63 %, m.p.: 221-222. Mol, formula C₂₁H₂₀O₇. Mol. Wt: 384.38. Elemental analysis calc. C, 65.62; H, 5.24, found: C, 65.53; H, 5.01. IR (KBr) (cm⁻¹): 3479 (OH) & 1654 (CO). ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆): δ 4.12, 4.00, 3.99, 3.97 (4s, 12H, 4OCH₃); 7.55, 6.80 (sd, 3H, ArH); 6.55, 6.36 (dd, 2H, J=2.50 Hz, CH=CH); 7.57, 6.61 (dd, 2H, J=2.40 Hz, furan ring); 9.88 (s, 1H, OH, exchangeable D₂O). Exact Mass: 384.12, m/e: 384.09 (79.2%), 385.09 (11.1%), 386.10 (22.1%).

General procedure for synthesis of Pyrrole rings

To the mixture of Chalcone **3c** (1 mmol) hydrazine hydrate/or phenyl hydrazine respectively (1 mmol), in ethanol (25ml) and triethylamine was added. The mixture was refluxed for 3hr. The reaction was monitored by TLC. After the complete disappearance of starting materials, the reaction mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure. Then the reaction mixture was diluted with ethyl acetate and water. The organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ followed by concentration of solvent by rotary evaporator under reduced pressure. The desired product from the crude was isolated by silica-gel column chromatography using ethyl acetate/hexanes (2:8) in excellent.

5-(4,5-dihydro-3-(4-nitrophenyl)-1H-pyrazol-5-yl)-4,7-dimethoxybenzofuran-6-ol **5a**:

Brown, yield %66, m.p.: 187-189 °C Mol, formula C₁₉H₁₇N₃O₆. Mol. Wt: 383.35. Elemental analysis: calc. C, 59.53; H, 4.47; N, 10.96. Found: C, 59.21; H, 4.21; N, 10.75. IR (KBr) (cm⁻¹): 3472 (OH) & 3218 (NH); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆): δ 2.02, 1.87 (d, 2CH, CH₂ Pyrazole ring); 3.92 (t, 1H, CH Pyrazole ring); 4.10, 4.00 (ss, 6H, 2OCH₃); 5.46 (s, 1H, NH, exchangeable D₂O); 7.56, 6.66 (dd, 2H, J=2.1 Hz, furan ring) and 8.88 (s, 1H, OH, exchangeable D₂O). Exact Mass: 383.11, m/e: 383.11 (33.2%), 384.12 (21.1%), 385.12 (22.7%).

5-(4,5-dihydro-3-(4-nitrophenyl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5-yl)-4,7-dimethoxybenzofuran-6-ol **5b**:

Brown, yield 53%, m.p.: 265 °C decomposition. Mol. formula C₂₅H₂₁N₃O₆. Mol. Wt: 459.45. Elemental analysis: calc. C, 65.35; H, 4.61; N, 9.15, found: C, 65.00; H, 4.42; N, 8.88. IR (KBr) (cm⁻¹): 3472 (OH) & 3218 (NH); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆): δ 2.00, 1.80 (d, 2CH, CH₂ Pyrazole ring); 3.90 (t, 1H, CH Pyrazole ring); 4.00, 3.99 (ss, 6H, 2OCH₃); 5.50 (s, 1H, NH, exchangeable D₂O); 7.56, 6.66 (dd, 2H, J=2.1 Hz, furan ring); 8.00, 7.88 (dd, 4H, ArH); 7.72-6.44 (m, 5H, ArH); and 8.88 (s, 1H, OH, exchangeable D₂O). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) ppm: 34.4, 40.8, 56.6, 56.5, 105.9, 110.7, 111.0, 113.8, 117.6, 121.3, 122.7, 130.0, 130.4, 140.5, 142.4, 143.3, 145.6, 146.3, 146.6, 150.8, 151.9. Exact Mass: 459.14, m/e: 459.14 (74.7%), 460.15 (28.1%), 461.15 (12.4%).

5,6-dihydro-6-(6-hydroxy-4,7-dimethoxybenzofuran-5-yl)-4-(4-nitrophenyl)pyrimidine-2(1H)-thione **6**:

A mixture of Chalcone **3c** (1 mmol), thiourea (1mmol) and sodium ethoxide (24 mL, 0.5 M) was stirred in EtOH (30 mL) at 40 °C for about 6 h under an air atmosphere. After completion of reaction (monitored by TLC), the reaction

mixture was poured into distilled water, and the formed precipitate was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol. The filtrate was neutralized to pH ~7.0 with dilute hydrochloric acid and the formed crude precipitate was filtered, washed several times with distilled water and dried

Brown, yield % 66, m.p.: 187-189 °C Mol, formula C₂₀H₁₇N₃O₆S. Mol.Wt: 427.43. Elemental analysis Found: C, 56.20; H, 4.01; N, 9.83; S, 7.50. calc. C, 55.98; H, 3.88; N, 9.80; S, 7.43. IR (KBr) (cm⁻¹): 3478 (OH) & 3218 (NH); ¹H NMR (DMSO- *d*₆): δ 1.59 (d, 2CH, CH₂ thiopyrimidine ring); 3.94 (t, 1H, CH thiopyrimidine ring); 4.10, 4.12 (ss, 6H, 2OCH₃); 5.99 (s, 1H, NH, exchangeable D₂O); 7.66, 6.68 (dd, 2H, J=2.1 Hz, furan ring); 8.11, 8.00 (dd, 4H, aromatic ring) and 8.53 (s, 1H, OH, exchangeable D₂O). ¹³C NMR (62.5 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 187.7; 166.2; 150.8; 146.6; 146.3; 145.6; 143.2; 139.8; 130.2; 122.7; 121.0; 111.1; 110.5; 103.1; 56.7; 56.6; 43.3; 33.2. Exact Mass: 427.08, m/e: 427.08 (19.2%), 428.08 (11.1%), 429.08 (22.1%).

Biological Activity

Cells

Cell lines: non-small cell lung (A549) and melanoma skin (A375) were obtained from American Type Culture Collection (Rockville, Maryland, USA) and are being maintained in the Ludwik Hirszfeld Institute of Immunology and Experimental Therapy (Wrocław, Poland). Cells were cultured in Eagle medium (IET, Wrocław, Poland) supplemented with 2 mM L-glutamine, 10% fetal bovine serum, 8 µg/mL of insulin and 1% mem non-essential amino acid solution 100x (all from Sigma–Aldrich Chemie GmbH, Steinheim, Germany). BALB/3T3 cell line was cultured in DMEM (Gibco, UK) supplemented with 2 mM L-glutamine, 10% fetal bovine serum (GE Healthcare, Logan, UT, USA). All culture media were also supplemented with antibiotics: 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Sigma–Aldrich Chemie GmbH, Steinheim, Germany) and 100 units/ml penicillin (PolfaTarchomin SA, Warsaw, Poland). All cell lines were grown at 37 °C with 5% CO₂ humidified atmosphere.

Compounds

Prior to usage, the compounds were dissolved in DMSO (stock solution 10 mg/ml) and culture medium (1:9) to the concentration of 1 mg/ml and subsequently diluted in culture medium to reach the required concentrations (ranging from 100 to 0.1 µg/ml, only one compound 3a was tested in different range of concentrations from 10 to 0.01 µg/ml, because of small amount of tested compound).

An anti-proliferative assay *in vitro*

24 hours before addition of the tested compounds, the cells were plated in 96-well plates (Sarstedt, Germany) at density of 1x10⁴ cells per well. The assay was performed after 72 hours exposure to varying concentrations of the tested compounds. The *in vitro* cytotoxic effect of all compounds was examined using the SRB assay.

Cytotoxic test SRB

The details of this technique were described by Skehan *et al* [16]. The cells were attached to the bottom of plastic wells by fixing them with cold 50% TCA (trichloroacetic acid, Sigma-Aldrich Chemie GmbH, Steinheim, Germany) on the top of the culture medium in each well. The plates were incubated at 4°C for 1 hour and then washed five times with tap water. The cellular material fixed with TCA was stained with 0.4% sulphorhodamine B (SRB, Sigma-Aldrich Chemie GmbH, Steinheim, Germany) dissolved in 1% acetic acid (POCH, Gliwice, Poland) for 30 minutes. Unbound dye was removed by rinsing (five times) in 1% acetic acid. The protein-bound dye was extracted with 10 mM unbuffered Tris base (POCH, Gliwice, Poland) for determination of the optical density (λ = 540 nm) in Synergy H4 multi-mode microplate reader (BioTek Instruments USA).

The relation between surviving fraction and drug concentration is plotted to get the survival curve for each cell line after the specified time. The concentration required for 50% inhibition of cell viability (IC₅₀) was calculated and the results are given in Table 1. The results were compared to the antiproliferative effects of the reference control doxorubicin [17].

Statistical Analysis: The results are reported as Mean ± Standard error (S.E.) for at least six times experiments.

Results and Discussion

The Chalcones **3b,c,e** were proceeded by Schoenberg [5], Hishmat [6], Chiara [7] and the Chalcones **3a,d** [8-12] were according to the synthetic process [13] by condensation of molar equivalents of ketone **1** with aldehyde compounds namely: p-anisaldehyde and 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde in alcoholic KOH (10%) at room temperature for 1hr. (Scheme 1). All the spectra and analytic analysis of compounds **3a,d** were in the accordance with the suggested structure. The ¹H NMR for product **3d** as example was showed 2 doublets protons at δ 6.55, 6.36 ppm. Moreover, the mass spectroscopy of **3d** showed a molecular ion peak at 384.09 (79.2%).

Figure 1: Synthesis of compounds **3a-e**

Figure 2: Synthesis of compounds **5a, b** and **6**

Pyrazole ring [14] was very important and had many applications. Pyrazole [10-12] compounds **3a,b** were synthesized at the refluxing of Chalcone **3c** with equimolar amount of hydrazine hydrate/ or phenyl hydrazine in absolute alcohol/ triethylamine. Also, dihydropyrimidine-2(1H)-thione [15] ring **6** was prepared at condensation of Chalcone **3c** with equimolar amount thiourea in boiling absolute ethanol in the presence of sodium hydroxide. The structure products **5a,b** and **6** were established by both analytical and spectral data. The IR spectra of product **5b** for example revealed the absence of carbonyl absorption band of Chalcone **3c** and new absorption band of NH group was appeared at 3218 cm⁻¹. In addition, the ¹H NMR of product **5b** showed two doublets at δ 2.00, 1.80 ppm, of CH₂ in Pyrazole rings and one triplet at δ 3.90 ppm of CH in Pyrazole rings. Also, in ¹³C NMR spectrum showed

21 signals for product **5b** resonated at 34.4 due to (CH Pyrazole ring), 40.8 due to (CH₂ Pyrazole ring), 56.6, 46.5 due to (2 OCH₃) and 105.9, 110.7, 111.0, 113.8, 117.6, 121.3, 122.7, 130.0, 130.4, 140.5, 142.4, 143.3, 145.6, 146.3, 146.6, 150.8, 151.9. Mass spectroscopy of **5b** showed a molecular ion peak at m/e: 459.14 (74.7%).

Antiproliferative Activity of the Tested Compounds

The antiproliferative activities were expressed by median growth inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀). As shown in table 1, the *in vitro* antiproliferative activity towards two different human non-small cell lung (A549) and melanoma skin (A375) cancer cell lines in addition to BALB/3T3 (murine fibroblast) normal cell line was evaluated using SRB assay, in comparison with doxorubicin as reference drug.

The results revealed that most compounds showed variable activity against human melanoma skin (A375) and lung A549 cancer cells. The tumor cell line showed normal growth in our culture system and DMSO did not seem to have any noticeable effect on cellular growth. A gradual decrease in viability of cancer cells was observed with increasing concentration of the tested compounds, in a dose-dependent inhibitory effect.

For melanoma skin (A375) cancer cells, while compound **3** had no effect on these cancer cells, compound **6** was found to be more potent than the standard drug, doxorubicin anticancer agent with IC₅₀ value 2.6 ± 0.08 μg/ml versus 3.8 ± 0.2 μg/ml for doxorubicin. On the other hand, compounds **3b** and **5a** were found to be potent anticancer agents had IC₅₀ values near to the standard drug (IC₅₀: 4.9 ± 0.6, 4.5 ± 0.06 and 7.93 ± 1.08 μg/ml respectively versus 3.8 ± 0.2 μg/ml for doxorubicin). In the same sense, evaluation the anticancer effect of the tested compounds towards human on-small cell lung (A549) cancer cells revealed that compounds **2b, 5a** and **6** showed anticancer activity closed to the standard drug (IC₅₀: 6.2 ± 0.9, 7.9 ± 0.4, 10.8 ± 0.5 and 4.7 ± 0.1 μg/ml respectively, versus 2.7 ± 0.06 μg/ml for doxorubicin).

However, these compounds (**3b, 5a** and **6**) showed slight or moderate activity towards normal cell line BALB/3T3 (the IC₅₀ values are 81.31 ± 9.7, 88.04 ± 9.7, 64.09 ± 12.03 and 53.24 ± 8.65 μg/ml, respectively).

In conclusion, Chalcone **3a, d** as starting material was synthesized at the reaction of ketone with acetyl compound derivatives Also, Chalcone **3c** was reacted with hydrazine hydrate/ or phenyl hydrazine/ or thiourea to give Pyrazole rings **5a, b** and dihydropyrimidine-2(1*H*)-thione ring **6**. The tested compounds exert anti-proliferative activity on human non-small cell lung (A549) and melanoma skin (A375) cancer cell lines through reducing the cell proliferation and resulted in significant growth inhibitory effect. Although compounds **3b** and **5a** showed cytotoxicity and growth inhibitor activity on both lung and skin cancer cell lines with IC₅₀ values near to the standard drug, compound **6** was found to be more potent than the doxorubicin in skin cancer cell line. Moreover, the present study reveals that melanoma skin (A375) cells are more sensitive to the tested compounds than the non-small cell lung (A549) cells.

Table 1: The *In vitro* cytotoxic activity of the tested compounds towards human non-small cell lung (A549) and melanoma skin (A375) cancer as well as normal BALB/3T3 cell lines is expressed as IC₅₀ values.

Compound	Lung (A549) IC ₅₀	Skin (A375) IC ₅₀	BALB/3T3 IC ₅₀
1	25.9±3.2	N.A.	N.A.
3a	22.8±2.9	4.1 ± 0.1	N.A.
3b	6.2±0.9	4.9±0.6	81.31 ± 9.7
2c	36.5±0.6	52.8±0.6	N.A.
3e	42.3±0.5	14.9±0.9	96.45±10.3
5a	10.8± 0.5	7.93 ± 1.08	64.09 ± 12.03
5b	64.09 ± 12.00	39.85 ± 1.17	59.76 ± 8.07
6	4.7 ± 0.1	2.6±0.08	53.24 ± 8.65
Doxorubicin	2.7 ± 0.06	3.8 ± 0.2	19.05 ± 1.4
DMSO	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.

Data were expressed as Mean ± SD of six independent experiments.

N.A. is no activity

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